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Evaluation of different magnetic
capture protocols for the
detection of
Echinococcus multilocularis
DNA in red foxes.

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EVALUATION OF DIFFERENT MAGNETIC CAPTURE PROTOCOLS FOR THE DETECTION OF *ECHINOCOCCUS MULTILOCULARIS* DNA IN RED FOXES

1. Introduction

1.1. Epidemiological context

This work forms part of JRP-WP4-T3 Organisation of selected PTs from WP2 and WP3 of the One Health EJP project Multi-centre study on *Echinococcus multilocularis* and *Echinococcus granulosus* s.l. in Europe: development and harmonization of diagnostic methods in the food chain (MEME). Four laboratories tested and evaluated different magnetic capture protocols for the detection of *E. multilocularis* DNA in red fox faeces.

Current gold standard for the detection of *E. multilocularis* in definitive hosts is reliant on the detection of adult parasites in the intestine using either intestinal scraping technique or sedimentation counting techniques. Both these methods are labour intensive and the screening of a large number of samples very time consuming. A number of different molecular methods have been developed to detect low levels of *E. multilocularis* DNA in fox faeces in order to allow rapid screening of a large number of samples¹⁻⁴. The aims of this study were to compare the performance of one method at two different laboratories using standardized samples (study 1) and also to compare the different methods used by different laboratories (study 2) by testing homogenized standardized proficiency test samples.

1.2. References

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²Øines, Ø., Isaksson, M., Hagström, Å. *et al.* Laboratory assessment of sensitive molecular tools for detection of low levels of *Echinococcus multilocularis*-eggs in fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces. *Parasites Vectors* **7**, 246 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1756-3305-7-246>

³Maas, M., van Roona, A., Dam-Deisz, C. *et al.* Evaluation by latent class analysis of a magnetic capture based DNA extraction followed by real-time qPCR as a new diagnostic method for detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in definitive hosts. *Veterinary Parasitology* **230**, 20-24 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2016.10.016>

⁴Maksimov, P., Isaksson, M., Schares, G. *et al.* Validation of PCR-based protocols for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA in the final host using the Intestinal Scraping Technique as a reference. *Food and Waterborne Parasitology* **15**, e00044 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fawpar.2019.e00044>

⁵Tackmann, K., Löschner, U., Mix, H. *et al.* A field study to control *Echinococcus multilocularis*-infections of the red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) in an endemic focus. *Epidemiology and Infection* **127**(3), 577-587 (2001). <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0950268801006112>

⁶Staubach, C., Hoffmann, L., Schmid, V.J. *et al.* Bayesian space–time analysis of *Echinococcus multilocularis*-infections in foxes. *Veterinary Parasitology* **179**(1-3), 77-83 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2011.01.065>

⁷Maksimov, P., Schares, G., Press, S. *et al.* Comparison of different commercial DNA extraction kits and PCR protocols for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* eggs in faecal samples from foxes. *Veterinary Parasitology* **237**, 83-93 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vetpar.2017.02.015>

⁸Hamnes, I.S., Enemark, H.L., Henriksen, K. *et al.* The surveillance program for *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) in Norway. Annual Report, Norwegian Veterinary Institute:7 (2020). https://www.vetinst.no/overvaking/revens-dvergbendelmark-echinococcus/_attachment/download/a228fc46-db96-4310-8cbd-da1795aec751:5f7ed7483aba1c8823a13a69d3200325a78fd2a4/2020_OK_E.multilocularis_Report%202019.pdf

⁹Davidson, R., Henriksen, K., Øines, Ø. SOP Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test. *Zenodo* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6046190>

¹⁰Øines, Ø., Henriksen, K., Lukacs, M. *et al.* SOP Magnetic capture of *Echinococcus multilocularis* DNA from red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples: DNA extraction with manual washing steps (Version 1). *Zenodo* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4897969>

2. Material and methods

Two studies were carried out for the inter-laboratory validation of the magnetic capture methods. The first study involved two laboratories following MC-PCR method published by Maas *et al.*³ whilst the second study involved four participating laboratories using four different MC-PCR methods.

Study 1. Samples for inter-laboratory validation of magnetic capture protocol – using the same MC-PCR as described by Maas *et al.*, 2016

Fox faeces artificially spiked with a known number of *E. multilocularis* eggs

Two sets of samples with defined numbers of *E. multilocularis* eggs were prepared, one each for the participating laboratories at this stage of the inter-laboratory comparisons. Each set contained three samples per egg concentration, with either 1, 5, 50, or 500 *E. multilocularis* eggs added to red fox faeces that had previously tested negative for the parasite, giving a total of 12 samples per set. For each run positive, negative, and extraction blank controls were included.

The *E. multilocularis* eggs were isolated from the faeces of naturally infected foxes following the protocols described in Maksimov *et al.*⁴ and Øines *et al.*². The positive foxes came from naturally infected individuals that had been hunted in the federal state of Brandenburg, Germany in 2008.

The two laboratories that received the set with a defined number of eggs, added 1 gram of negative fox faeces to each sample prior to carrying out the magnetic capture protocol and Realtime PCR described by Maas *et al.*³. The negative fox faeces were obtained from foxes, hunted in Brandenburg that had tested negative by intestinal scraping technique (IST)^{5,6} and previously by PCR analysis⁷.

Screening of red fox faeces with natural infections

Twenty faecal samples from red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) known to be either naturally infected with, or negative for, *E. multilocularis* based IST screening carried out previously at Lab 1 were also screened using the Maas *et al.*³ method at both laboratories. In brief, two 1-gram faecal samples were taken from each individual giving two sets with twenty samples. The samples in each set were attributed one of three infection intensity groups, based on the IST results (Table 1).

<i>E. multilocularis</i> status after IST analysis	No. samples/set
Negative	5
1-5 <i>E. multilocularis</i> adults detected in intestine – low burden of infection	10
5-50 <i>E. multilocularis</i> adults detected in intestine – moderate burden of infection	5

Table 1: Showing the abundance of *Echinococcus multilocularis* infection in the intestines of red foxes (*Vulpes vulpes*) that had faecal samples analysed as part of study 1 Inter-laboratory comparison of magnetic capture methods

Study 2. Samples for inter-laboratory validation of magnetic capture protocol – in four labs

Homogenisation of red fox faecal samples

Red fox faeces that had previously tested negative for *E. multilocularis* in the Norwegian *E. multilocularis* annual surveillance from program (from 2019)⁸ were homogenized as one batch. Mainland Norway is still considered a region free from *E. multilocularis* infection⁸. Initially 65 red fox faecal samples were pooled in six batches and homogenized in stomacher bags at maximum setting for 10 minutes. Bones and other hard masses were removed prior to, and after homogenisation for those that had been overlooked initially. The homogenised material from the six stomacher bags was divided between two new stomacher bags and the homogenization step repeated. The two bags were then combined and homogenization repeated a third and final time. The homogenized faeces were divided between 50 mL conical tubes each containing 50 grams of homogenized faeces (N=5) and 15mL falcon tubes preloaded with zirconium beads (N=69), each containing 3 g of faeces.

Preparation of positive *E. multilocularis* material

Ten *E. multilocularis* adult worms per cryotube, obtained during sedimentation counting technique of arctic fox intestines, from Svalbard where *E. multilocularis* is endemic, were fixed in 70 % ethanol in 1 mL cryotubes and stored frozen at -80 °C. Six cryotubes containing this positive material were prepared. All the positive material came from the same animal.

Fox faeces artificially spiked with a known number of *E. multilocularis* eggs – verification material

Each participating laboratory received a cryotube with adult *E. multilocularis* and a tube of 50 g of homogenized faeces to carry out method verification. Each laboratory was responsible for making their own verification material samples containing red fox faeces spiked with 1, 5, 10 and whole worms as per the verification protocol described in the SOP Verification of *Echinococcus multilocularis* magnetic capture method in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faeces and proficiency test⁹. In total six faecal samples and two blank samples were spiked with either 1 egg, 5 eggs, 10 eggs or a whole worm respectively. Samples were then analysed using the magnetic capture method with manual washing steps¹⁰ followed by qPCR analysis using either a published² or in-house method (in-house PCR targeting mitochondrial DNA [manuscript in prep.]). When at least one of the duplicates in the verification panel for each egg concentration was PCR positive then the sample was considered positive. If the extraction blank control and negative control were positive, or if the spiked faecal samples were negative the verification panel was not approved.

Fox faeces artificially spiked with whole adult worms or segments of worms – proficiency test material

Each participating laboratory also received a set of proficiency test containing 10 samples. This set was made by spiking, with either a whole adult or a segment of an adult, seven of 15 mL falcon tubes preloaded with zirconium beads and 3 g homogenized faeces. A further three tubes with the homogenized faeces were left blank and were not spiked with *E. multilocularis* material. The participating laboratories used their established methods for the detection of *E. multilocularis* in the samples. Three of the four participating laboratories carried out the magnetic capture method as described in (Manual washing SOP) termed MC1 whilst the remaining laboratory used their own magnetic capture protocol

MC2 (Table 2). The laboratories subsequently analysed the DNA using the magnetic capture method, either MC1 1 or MC2 3, and qPCR method of their own choice¹⁻³ (or in-house method).

Study	Lab ID	Magnetic Capture method	PCR protocol
1	1	MC2	Maas et al. 2016 ³
2	1	MC1	Isaksson et al. 2014 ¹
1&2	2	MC2	Maas et al. 2016 ³
2	3	MC1	In-house qPCR (MS in prep.)
2	4	MC1	Øines et al. 2014 ²

Table 2: Showing how the different laboratories participate in the two different inter-laboratory comparisons for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples using spiked materials based on magnetic capture methods described in Isaksson et al.1 (MC1) or Maas et al.3 (MC2) and four different qPCR protocols¹⁻³.

Statistical analysis

Analysis of the results from first study with the two laboratories testing the Maas et al. method³ in an inter-laboratory comparison used R (version 3.5.1) for the statistical computing and graphical presentation of the results (Team, 2018). For statistical comparison of Ct values between the protocols, the Mann-Whitney test from the R package “stats” was used. To test the null hypothesis, no difference in performance between the two laboratories, the “pairwise.fisher.test” function from the package “fmsb” was applied.

Analysis of the results from the four laboratories that analysed samples in the second study was done in the JMP Pro 14.0.0 program (SAS Institute Inc.). Simple two by two tables were constructed to estimate the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and agreement statistic for the different laboratories. Given the small sample size, only 10 analyses for three laboratories and just 19 for the final laboratory further statistical analysis was not carried out.

For all statistical analyses a significance level of $p < 0.05$ was selected.

3. Results

For the MC1 (Table 2) method, studies comparing the validation and reproducibility of the MC1 method have already been performed^{2,4}.

Study 1 - Fox faeces artificially spiked with a known number of *E. multilocularis* eggs

The validation and reproducibility of the MC2 method³ (Table 2) was performed between two laboratories (Lab1 and Lab2) in this study. In the first step, the MC2 protocol was validated in parallel in two laboratories using the artificially spiked faecal samples.

Results of this analysis showed that all artificially spiked samples, except for the samples those with one egg, could be evaluated as positive in both laboratories (Table 3). Similar results were obtained in the two laboratories using the same method and the differences in detection between the two were not statistically significant. The Ct results from Lab1 were however significantly higher than those from Lab2.

No. of eggs in 1 g negative fox faeces	Lab1	Lab2
500	26.97	23.79
500	27.69	24.1
500	26.36	21.14
50	28.9	27.87
50	30.14	27.55
50	29.56	29
5	35.29	31.72
5	37.74	34.13
5	37.47	32.53
1	40.62	Neg
1	44.47	Neg
1	40.71	37.57

Table 2: qPCR results (Ct values) from Inter-laboratory comparison of the magnetic capture protocol (MC2) using artificially spiked faecal samples at Lab1 and Lab2 (protocol 1).

Study 1- Screening of red fox faeces with natural infections

Faecal samples of red foxes that had already been examined for *E. multilocularis* using IST (Table 4) were tested by Lab1 and Lab2 using MC2 magnetic capture and PCR as described by Maas et al.³.

Red fox intestine (IST)	Faeces PCR positive	Faeces PCR negative	Total
Parasite positive	15	15	30
Parasite negative	1	9	10
Total	16	24	40

Table 3: Overall results of the forty samples examined by Lab1 and Lab2 using the Maas et al. (2016) magnetic capture and PCR method for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in naturally infected red fox (*Vulpes vulpes*) faecal samples.

Neither of the laboratories was able to correctly identify all the samples. There were no statistically significant differences between the laboratories in the number of positive samples or in the Ct values (Table 5).

Lab ID	Magnetic Capture Protocol	PCR	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive predictive value	Negative predictive value
Lab 1	MC2	Maas et al. 2016	0.53	1	1	0.42
Lab 2	MC2	Maas et al. 2016	0.47	0.8	0.88	0.33
Both Labs			0.5	0.9	0.94	0.38

Table 4: The performance of the magnetic capture method at two laboratories using the magnetic capture and PCR methods described in Maas et al. 2016 compared to intestinal scraping technique (IST) result as reference standard. Twenty duplicate fox faecal samples were screened by both laboratories. These foxes had previously tested negative (N=5), positive with low levels of infection (1-5 adults in the intestine, N=10) or positive with moderate levels of infection (5-50 adults in the intestine, N=5) by IST examination.

Study 2 – Verification using homogenised faeces spiked with *E. multilocularis* eggs.

Two laboratories (Lab3 and Lab4) carried out the verification protocol prior to the analysis of the proficiency test⁹. Both laboratories reported identifying all 32 spiked samples correctly, including all six faecal samples spiked with one egg only, as well as all the negative and extraction blank controls being negative.

Study 2 – Proficiency test: Fox faeces artificially spiked with whole adult worms or segments of worms

Four laboratories evaluated the panel of ten fox faecal samples sent to each laboratory. Lab1 also analysed an additional nine samples that were available. Each laboratory carried out their own preferred method of magnetic capture and PCR protocols. In total 49 samples were analysed by the four laboratories that reported their results in the proficiency test using different magnetic capture DNA extraction methods followed by four different PCR methods^{1-3, in-house} (Table 6, Table 7). The overall sensitivity of the tests was 88% whilst the specificity was 94% when looking at the dataset as a whole (Table 7) with substantial agreement (kappa co-efficient 0.78) between the PCR methods and the presence or absence of *E. multilocularis* in spiked samples. Notably the two laboratories (N=20 samples) that carried out the verification step prior to analysing the proficiency test material had 100% sensitivity and specificity, both using the MC1 DNA extraction method, but with two different realtime PCR methods (Table 7).

	PCR positive	PCR negative	Total
Parasite positive	29	4	33
Parasite negative	1	15	16
Total	30	19	49

Table 5: Overall results of the forty nine samples examined by Lab1, Lab2, Lab3 and Lab4 using different magnetic capture and PCR methods for the detection of *Echinococcus multilocularis* in homogenised red fox faecal samples spiked with either whole *E. multilocularis* worms, segments of worms or not spiked (parasite negative faeces).

Two of the laboratories correctly identified all the positive and negative samples in their proficiency test set (Lab3 and Lab4) whilst Lab1 correctly identified 15 of the 19 samples tested (one false positive and three false negatives) and Lab2 correctly identified all but 1 of the 10 samples (a false negative).

Lab. Id	Verification material analysed (Y/N)	Magnetic capture method	PCR method	No. samples analysed	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive predictive value	Negative predictive value
1	N	MC1	1	19	0.77	0.83	0.91	0.63
2	N	MC2	2	10	0.86	1	1	0.75
3	Y	MC1	3	10	1	1	1	1
4	Y	MC1	4	10	1	1	1	1
<i>All labs</i>		<i>Both</i>	<i>All</i>	<i>49</i>	<i>0.88</i>	<i>0.94</i>	<i>0.97</i>	<i>0.79</i>

Table 6: Summary of the performance of the different magnetic capture and PCR methods used by four different laboratories to screen homogenised red fox faecal sample that had been spiked with whole *E. multilocularis* worms, segments of worm or left unspiked.

4. Discussion

The sensitivity of the MC-PCR assay used in study 1 ranged from 47-53%, but was not significantly different between the two laboratories. The majority of the samples came from red foxes that had low

numbers of *E. multilocularis* adults in their intestines. The shedding of eggs and worm segments will not be homogenous and therefore it is possible that the faecal samples taken from these individuals, given that just 1 gram of faeces was examined from each individual at each laboratory, did not contain sufficiently high amounts of parasite DNA to enable detection. The results from the spiked faecal samples show that the MC-PCR method is capable of detection of one egg per gram at both laboratories. Inhibition of the PCR needs to also be considered when considering the spiked sample results, since the faeces used for preparing the spiked samples originated from different foxes in the regions of each of the participating laboratories.

The sensitivity of the MC-PCR assays used in study 2 ranged from 77-100%, but the samples contained either whole worms or segments of worms and not just eggs as in study 1. Ideally the laboratories should have used the same MC-PCR methods throughout, as done in study 1, for true inter-laboratory comparisons. But the advantage of testing homogenised samples spiked with potentially high levels of DNA (whole worms/segments of *E. multilocularis* worms) is that it can show differences in the performance of the different magnetic capture and PCR methods at each laboratory. The next step would be to repeat the proficiency test ensuring that each lab tested the other methods employed by the others in addition to their own. The subsequent results matrix would reveal if the variation seen in the test performance is method or laboratory specific. Study 1 indicated that the performance between the two laboratories testing the MC2³ method varied albeit not significantly. Such further testing was outside the timeframe and scope of this task.

Further conclusions regarding interlaboratory differences are harder to draw. The two laboratories that had the highest sensitivity and specificity both carried out an initial verification step, prior to carrying out the proficiency test, using homogenised faeces and *E. multilocularis* eggs that came from the same batch as those used in the proficiency test. Perhaps this initial testing of the same source material could in part explain the higher sensitivity at these two laboratories. The false positive sample identified by one laboratory is harder to interpret. The faecal sample was divided into the falcon tubes prior to handling positive material and therefore the chance of cross-contamination at the laboratory that prepared the proficiency tests is highly unlikely. There is also of course a chance the faeces used was not negative. However, all samples had previously been screened individually for *E. multilocularis*⁸ and came from a non-endemic region for the parasite. All other negative proficiency test samples in the homogenised faeces tested negative. Another possible explanation could be that samples were switched by human error during the analysis process.

The four false negative samples were all flagged as only containing a segment of adult *E. multilocularis* worms rather than whole worms. The laboratory that used MC2³ magnetic capture protocol subdivided the proficiency test samples into three 1-gram samples prior to magnetic capture. It is therefore possible that the worm segment was not contained in the subsamples taken for further analysis. The other laboratory with false negatives did not do this and given that PCR inhibition was not seen in the other samples, made with the same homogenised faeces, further investigation is needed to explore why these samples tested negative. The remaining two laboratories also received samples with only worm segments and were able to correctly identify them as positive.

Despite this, these proficiency test results show that these methods have high sensitivity and specificity but that the methods used need to be tested and verified at each laboratory. The use of verification material is therefore strongly recommended to confirm that the staff carrying out the analysis, as well as controlling that the reagents and equipment being used, give sufficiently reliable results.